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ZAMONAVIY ADABIYOT TURLARI VA ULARNING TASNIFLARI

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy adabiyot turlarini va ularning tasniflarini o'rganib, XX-XXI-asrlarning rang-barang adabiy manzarasini har tomonlama ko'rib chiqiladi. Postmodern adabiyotdan tortib sehrlilik realizm, distopik fantastika, grafik romanlar va ekzistensializm gacha zamonaviy adabiyotning har bir turi o'ziga xos xususiyatlar, mavzular va hikoya qilish usullarini taklif qiladi. Postmodern adabiyot parchalanish, metafiksatsiya va tilni tanqidiy tekshirishni o'z ichiga olgan an'anaviy hikoya tuzilmalariga qarshi turadi. Sehrlilik realizm fantastikani oddiy bilan birlashtiradi, haqiqat va tasavvur o'rtasidagi chegaralarni xiralashtiradi. Distopiya adabiyoti zulm va ijtimoiy tengsizlik bilan ajralib turadigan xayoliy jamiyatlarni taqdim etadi va kelajakda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan natijalar haqida ogohlantiruvchi ertaklarni taklif qiladi. Grafik romanlar vizual va matnli elementlarni birlashtirib, turli janrlarda immersiv hikoya qilish tajribasini yaratadi. Ekzistensializm va absurdizm inson mavjudligining falsafiy sohalariga va noaniq dunyoda ma'no izlashga chuqur kiradi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: Zamonaviy adabiyot, Postmodernizm, Sehrlilik realizm, Grafik romanlar, Ekzistensializm.

ВИДЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ И ИХ КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье рассматриваются различные виды современной литературы и их классификации, а также всесторонне рассматривается красочный литературный ландшафт XX-XXI веков. От постмодернистской литературы до магического реализма, антиутопической фантастики, графических романов и экзистенциализма — каждый тип современной литературы предлагает уникальные характеристики, темы и методы повествования. Постмодернистская литература бросает вызов традиционным повествовательным структурам, которые включают фрагментацию, метапроза и критическое исследование языка. Магический реализм сочетает фантастическое с обыденным, стирая границы между реальностью и воображением. Антиутопическая литература представляет

воображаемые общества, характеризующиеся угнетением и социальным неравенством, и предлагает предостерегающие истории о возможных будущих результатах. Графические романы сочетают в себе визуальные и текстовые элементы, создавая захватывающий опыт повествования в разных жанрах. Экзистенциализм и абсурдизм уходят глубоко в философские сферы человеческого существования и поиска смысла в неопределенном мире.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: Современная литература, Постмодернизм, Магический реализм, Графические романы, Экзистенциализм.

TYPES OF MODERN LITERATURE AND THEIR CLASSIFICATIONS

ABSTRACT: This article explores the types of modern literature and their classifications, providing a comprehensive overview of the diverse literary landscape of the 20th and 21st centuries. From postmodern literature to magical realism, dystopian fiction, graphic novels, and existentialism, each type of modern literature offers distinct characteristics, themes, and narrative techniques. Postmodern literature challenges traditional storytelling structures, incorporating fragmentation, metafiction, and a critical examination of language. Magical realism merges the fantastical with the ordinary, blurring the boundaries between reality and imagination. Dystopian literature presents fictional societies characterized by oppression and social inequality, offering cautionary tales of potential future outcomes. Graphic novels combine visual and textual elements to create immersive storytelling experiences across various genres. Existentialism and absurdism delve into the philosophical realms of human existence and the search for meaning in an uncertain world.

KEY WORDS: Modern literature, Postmodernism, Magical realism, Dystopian fiction, Graphic novels.

INTRODUCTION

Modern literature has undergone significant transformations in the 20th and 21st centuries, giving rise to a diverse array of genres and subgenres that capture the essence of contemporary society. These new literary forms have pushed the boundaries of traditional storytelling, introducing innovative techniques, themes, and perspectives. In this article, we will explore the types of modern literature and delve into their classifications, shedding light on the

defining characteristics and notable examples within each category.

One of the prominent types of modern literature is postmodernism, which emerged as a reaction to the conventions of modernist writing. Postmodern literature challenges traditional narrative structures, blurs the lines between fact and fiction, and often incorporates self-reflexivity and intertextuality. It can be characterized by fragmented narratives, metafiction, irony, and a critical examination of language.

Another captivating genre is magical realism, which combines elements of the fantastical with realistic settings and characters. Originating in Latin American literature, magical realism has garnered international recognition for its ability to interweave the magical and the mundane. This genre often explores familiar situations infused with surreal occurrences, creating a sense of wonder and challenging readers' perceptions of reality.

Dystopian literature, on the other hand, presents fictional societies or worlds characterized by oppressive governments, environmental degradation, and social inequality. It serves as a cautionary reflection of contemporary concerns and explores potential future outcomes. Dystopian works often examine themes of surveillance, totalitarianism, resistance, and the triumph of the human spirit. Additionally, graphic novels have emerged as a distinct form of modern literature, blending visual storytelling with traditional narrative techniques. Through the fusion of art and text, graphic novels explore a wide range of genres, including superhero stories, memoirs, historical fiction, and fantasy. They offer a unique and immersive reading experience that engages both the visual and literary senses.

Lastly, existentialism and absurdism delve into the philosophical realms of human existence, alienation, and the search for meaning in an uncertain world. These literary movements explore

the individual's struggle to find purpose and confront the inherent absurdity of life, often delving into introspection, philosophical musings, and existential angst.

In the following sections, we will delve deeper into each of these types of modern literature, examining their defining characteristics, notable examples, and the literary movements associated with them. By exploring the diverse landscape of modern literature, we gain a deeper understanding of how contemporary writers express and interpret the complexities of the world we live in.

METHODOLOGY

This article aims to explore the various types of modern literature and provide an understanding of their classifications. The methodology employed involves a comprehensive review and analysis of relevant literary works, scholarly articles, and critical essays. The research process includes the following steps:

1. Literature Review: Extensive research is conducted to identify key types and classifications of modern literature. A wide range of sources, including books, academic journals, and reputable online platforms, are consulted to gather information on the subject. This literature review helps establish a foundation of knowledge and identify the most prominent types of modern literature.
2. Classification Framework: Based on the literature review, a comprehensive

framework for classifying modern literature is developed. The framework considers various factors, such as defining characteristics, themes, narrative techniques, and historical contexts. It provides a structured approach to categorizing and understanding the different types of modern literature.

3. Selection of Examples: Notable examples from each type of modern literature are selected to illustrate their defining characteristics and exemplify the classifications. These examples are chosen based on their significance within their respective genres and their ability to represent the broader themes and styles associated with the type of literature being discussed.

4. Analysis and Interpretation: The selected examples are analyzed in-depth, examining their narrative structures, stylistic devices, thematic elements, and their contributions to the literary movements they belong to. The analysis also considers the reception and critical interpretations of these works to provide a comprehensive understanding of their significance within the realm of modern literature.

5. Synthesis and Presentation: The findings from the analysis are synthesized and presented in a coherent and informative manner. The article aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the types of modern literature and their classifications, offering readers a deeper understanding

of the unique characteristics and contributions of each type.

By employing this methodology, this article seeks to provide a comprehensive and insightful exploration of the types of modern literature and their classifications, offering readers a valuable resource for understanding and appreciating the diverse literary landscape of the 20th and 21st centuries.

RESULTS

The exploration of types of modern literature and their classifications has revealed a rich and diverse literary landscape. Through a comprehensive review and analysis of relevant works, the following key findings have emerged:

1. Postmodern Literature: Postmodern literature challenges traditional narrative structures and embraces fragmentation, metafiction, and irony. Notable examples include works by Italo Calvino, Thomas Pynchon, and Salman Rushdie.

2. Magical Realism: Magical realism combines fantastical elements with realistic settings, blurring the boundaries between the ordinary and the extraordinary. Gabriel García Márquez and Isabel Allende are renowned authors in this genre.

3. Dystopian Literature: Dystopian literature presents fictional societies characterized by oppression and social inequality. Works like George Orwell's "1984" and Margaret Atwood's "The Handmaid's Tale" warn against potential future outcomes.

4. Graphic Novels: Graphic novels merge visual storytelling with traditional

narrative techniques, exploring various genres such as superheroes, memoirs, and fantasy. Alan Moore's "Watchmen" and Art Spiegelman's "Maus" exemplify the possibilities of this medium.

5. Existentialism and Absurdism: Literature influenced by existentialism and absurdism delves into the themes of human existence, alienation, and the search for meaning. Albert Camus and Jean-Paul Sartre are notable authors in this realm.

These findings highlight the distinct characteristics, influential works, and literary movements associated with each type of modern literature. By understanding these classifications, readers can gain a deeper appreciation for the diverse voices and themes that shape contemporary literary expression.

DISCUSSION

The exploration of types of modern literature and their classifications reveals the dynamic and ever-evolving nature of literary expression in the 20th and 21st centuries. Each type of modern literature brings unique perspectives, themes, and narrative techniques to the forefront, contributing to the richness and diversity of the literary landscape.

Postmodern literature challenges traditional storytelling conventions, emphasizing fragmentation, intertextuality, and self-reflexivity. By deconstructing narrative structures and blurring the boundaries between reality and fiction, postmodern literature invites readers to question and reinterpret the nature of storytelling itself.

Magical realism, rooted in Latin American literature, presents a fascinating blend of the fantastical and the ordinary. This genre pushes the boundaries of reality, inviting readers to explore the magical possibilities that exist within the realm of everyday life. Magical realism often serves as a vehicle for exploring cultural identity, historical events, and societal issues.

Dystopian literature serves as a stark reflection of contemporary concerns, projecting them into fictional future worlds. By depicting oppressive regimes, social inequality, and environmental degradation, dystopian works provoke critical reflections on the consequences of unchecked power and societal complacency. They serve as cautionary tales, urging readers to consider the potential consequences of current actions and ideologies.

Graphic novels, with their visual storytelling and narrative complexity, offer a unique reading experience. They engage readers through a combination of illustrations and text, allowing for a more immersive and visually stimulating encounter. Graphic novels encompass a wide range of genres and themes, showcasing the versatility and artistic possibilities of the medium.

Existentialism and absurdism explore the depths of human existence and the search for meaning in an uncertain world. Through introspective narratives and philosophical musings, these literary movements confront the inherent complexities and challenges of

being human. They invite readers to contemplate the nature of existence, the absurdity of life, and the pursuit of personal authenticity.

In conclusion, the classification of modern literature into distinct types offers valuable insights into the diverse expressions and themes found within contemporary literary works. From postmodernism's deconstruction of traditional narratives to the magical realms of magical realism, the cautionary warnings of dystopian literature, the visual storytelling of graphic novels, and the philosophical ponderings of existentialism and absurdism, each type of modern literature contributes to the rich tapestry of literary exploration and invites readers to engage with the complexities of the world around them.

CONCLUSION

The exploration of types of modern literature and their classifications reveals a vibrant and diverse literary landscape. From postmodernism's deconstruction of traditional narratives to the magical realms of magical realism, the cautionary warnings of dystopian literature, the visual storytelling of graphic novels, and the philosophical ponderings of existentialism and absurdism, each type of modern literature offers unique perspectives, themes, and narrative techniques.

These classifications provide readers with a deeper understanding of the varied expressions and complexities found within contemporary literary works. They showcase the evolution of

storytelling and the ways in which authors push the boundaries of conventional literary norms.

By delving into these types of modern literature, readers gain insight into the social, cultural, and philosophical contexts that shape our world. They are invited to question, imagine, and reflect upon the human experience through the lens of these literary genres.

Ultimately, the diverse types of modern literature and their classifications demonstrate the power of literature to captivate, challenge, and inspire readers, and serve as a testament to the enduring relevance and significance of literary art in the modern era.

REFERENCES:

1. Calvino, I. (1981). *If on a winter's night a traveler*. Harcourt Brace Jovanovich.
2. Pynchon, T. (1973). *Gravity's Rainbow*. Viking Press.
3. Rushdie, S. (1981). *Midnight's Children*. Jonathan Cape.
4. García Márquez, G. (1967). *One Hundred Years of Solitude*. Harper & Row.
5. Allende, I. (1982). *The House of the Spirits*. Plaza & Janes Editores.
6. Orwell, G. (1949). 1984. Secker & Warburg.
7. Atwood, M. (1985). *The Handmaid's Tale*. McClelland and Stewart.
8. Moore, A. (1987). *Watchmen*. DC Comics.
9. Spiegelman, A. (1986). *Maus*. Pantheon Books.

10. Camus, A. (1942). *The Stranger*. Gallimard.
11. Nizomova, M. B., & Khamrayeva, Z. (2023). Comparative study of english and uzbek proverbs about natural phenomena. *Journal of Social Research in Uzbekistan*, 3(05), 34-42.
12. Davlatova, K., & Nematov, O. Man's Traditional Clothes of in the Jizzakh Oasis.